

A Proposal to Initiate a Major Research Project

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First, let's quote the words of Guo Yanying (Chinese 郭衍莹), a famous scientist from our country's aerospace department: 'In summary, whether for positioning or time calibration, GPS and other satellite navigation systems do not require special "relativistic corrections". Therefore, hoping to use satellite navigation systems to confirm or disprove relativity is unrealistic.'

Reference: Guo Yanying, Do satellite navigation system clocks need 'correction' [N/OL]. Science Popularisation Times, 2020-09-11

https://digitalpaper.stdaily.com/http_www.kjrb.com/kjwzb/html/2020-09/11/content_453527.htm.

Professor Guo Yanying's above statement is just a summary of GPS positioning issues; the technical details have been discussed by Academician Tong Kai (Chinese 童铠) from China and GPS experts from the US, leading to the above conclusion.

What Professor Guo said firmly supports my research results; I am not casually siding with his opinion. I have my own independent research results, which oppose the mainstream view that Professor Guo said must be corrected using relativity theory. I cannot ignore this. The mainstream view is wrong, and the reason is that they do not

understand how the instrument, namely the atomic clock, works. Besides the links to my papers listed below, I now have new, deeper research results that I am not disclosing in this article, and I am not planning to debate, but I can give lectures to the mainstream; I can do popular science. I am not boasting at all by saying this; if I do not express my correct understanding, what reason would I have to propose the project topics below? This is the reason for my work, not a question of humility. Regardless of whether these mainstream researchers come from the US or other countries, the principle on which the instrument works does not change. Regarding these mainstream researchers, I will not discuss relativity for now because they do not even understand the basic working principle of the instrument; once the operation of the instrument is clarified, the issue of clock corrections will be clear.

An unfinished scientific research project that has lasted over a hundred years worldwide: the verification of relativity. Since 1919, when British astronomer Sir Arthur Stanley Eddington took photos during a solar eclipse, more experiments to verify relativity have appeared. However, almost all of these experiments share one basic feature: before the experiment, unrealistic goals were set, assuming the formulas of relativity were correct and then piecing together the data. For example, in the 1971 US global atomic clock experiment, a

description from a standard textbook is quoted: "The experimental results agree very well with the theoretical predictions of relativity." Such predetermined descriptions that conflict with the actual experimental results are very common in textbooks in Europe and the US.

After nearly two years of studying the US global atomic clock verification experiments and collecting subsequent data, I found that the experimental principles of the global atomic clock are incorrect and that the published experimental data is not true. My doubts about the experiment are entirely reasonable based on basic physics principles and are supported by real data. Dr A.G. Kelly once obtained the original data of the global atomic clock experiment from the US Navy observatory, but the data was messy and could not confirm relativistic time dilation. According to basic physics principles, no matter how much the clock's accuracy improves, it will not help with this experiment.

From my research on verifying time dilation in relativity, I reached an overall conclusion: any clock, regardless of its precision, whether an atomic clock, light clock, or nuclear clock, and whether on a plane or on a GPS satellite, has no possibility of verifying time dilation in relativity. Because there are many experiments on time dilation, and most verification experiments violate basic principles of physics and

lacked prior feasibility assessment, the focus here is on verifying the feasibility of the experimental principle. Therefore, it is necessary to carry out a large-scale project to examine feasibility and to address the feasibility assessment aspect of relativity verification experiments.

This research project considers starting from the first experimental verification of relativity, namely the 1919 solar eclipse photographic experiment that confirmed the curvature of spacetime according to relativity, and goes up to the 2015 gravitational wave experiment, supplementing feasibility studies on the principles of all relativity verification experiments over more than a hundred years. My description of this is, of course, completely in line with the established norms of scientific research. Moreover, I haven't involved any sensitive keywords—relativity; I'm just filling in the gaps regarding the verification experiments of relativity. Although this project is very ambitious, I already have some early advantages, and I intend to participate in this grand project as an ordinary researcher, or just part-time. My participation in this project won't crowd out job opportunities for young students. On the contrary, this project can provide more job opportunities for young students and, depending on the scale of the research group, can accommodate 10, dozens, or even over a hundred young students.

The topic of testing the feasibility of relativity is really necessary,

because if we don't understand the principles behind previous experiments, the next steps in physics will be unclear. It's like quantum theory, which started after relativity and now has many more practical applications. Relativity, when it comes to applications, mostly comes down to clock corrections for GPS positioning, but in fact, the start of using relativity for GPS corrections has been said to be unnecessary and not allowed in principle. This discussion has to be part of the feasibility evaluation. Only when the feasibility of verification experiments is clarified can various topics in particle and space research head in the right direction.

This article is just an argumentative piece, not a project proposal for a feasibility study, because I haven't received any authorisation to write such a project, so it isn't part of my job yet.

Related links:

1. Guo Yanying, Do satellite navigation system clocks need to be 'corrected' [N/OL]. Science Popularisation Times, 2020-09-11

Article link:

https://digitalpaper.stdaily.com/http_www.kjrb.com/kjwzb/html/2020-09/11/content_453527.htm.

2. Kelly, A. G. Hafele and Keating Tests: Did They Prove Anything? Galilean Electrodynamics, vol. 11, 2000.

Kelly, A. G. Hafele and Keating Tests: Did They Prove Anything?

Physics Essays, vol. 13, no. 4, December 2000.

Original link:

<https://www.cartesio-episteme.net/h&kpaper.htm>

3. Here's the link to the article where I question the Around-the-World Atomic Clock Experiments:

(1). Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑦

<https://zenodo.org/records/19758819>

(2). A mistaken experiment 50 years ago disrupted the direction of physics

<https://zenodo.org/records/19904457>

(3). Error Analysis On Around-The-World Atomic Clocks Experiments⑦

<https://vixra.org/abs/2602.0138>

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